

Part 1 - Original Articles - Peer-Reviewed

Section-1 : Comprehensive Articles

Individualized Homeopathic Treatment In The Management of Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia – A Case Series

Dr. Ramalingam Sitharthan^{1*}, Dr. Shahana Hakkim², Dr. Geethu Kolakkadan Ponnappan³

¹ MD (Hom)., Ph D (Hom)., Principal, Professor & HOD, Department of Practice of Medicine & Research Guide, National Homeopathy Research Institute in Mental Health (NHRIMH), Kottayam, Kerala.

² BHMS, Department of Practice of Medicine, National Homeopathy Research Institute in Mental Health (NHRIMH), Kottayam, Kerala.

³ BHMS, Department of Practice of Medicine, National Homeopathy Research Institute in Mental Health (NHRIMH), Kottayam, Kerala.

DOI: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20725809

J. Evid. Based Homeopath.2024:2(2):4-6.

*Address for correspondence

Dr. Ramalingam Sitharthan, MD (Hom)., Ph D (Hom)., Principal, Professor & HOD, Department of Practice of Medicine & Research Guide, National Homeopathy Research Institute in Mental Health (NHRIMH), Kottayam, Kerala. Former Professor & HOD in Practice of Medicine & Research Guide, Vinayaka Missions Homeopathic Medical College, Salem, Tamil Nadu.

Mobile: 9443203174

Email: sitharthan.r@gmail.com

Abstract

Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) is a benign enlargement of the prostate gland, commonly observed in men over 50 years of age, with peak incidence typically occurring between 60 and 70 years. If left untreated, it can progress to acute urinary retention and eventually requiring surgical intervention, significantly impacting the quality of life. To highlight the effectiveness of homeopathic treatment in reducing the size of the prostate gland in patients with benign prostatic hyperplasia, this is a case series of three patients suffering from BPH who visited the OPD of NHRIMH Kottayam during 2023-2024. Prostate weight on ultrasonography was assessed before and after treatment. All the cases received individualized homeopathic medicine internally based on repertorisation in reference with materia medica. After comparing the ultrasonographic reports, all the three cases showed a reduction in size of prostate gland after homeopathic intervention. Prostate gland becomes normal in two patients. *Lycopodium clavatum* was found to be the most effective remedy in two patients, while Sulphur proved most useful in one patient. This case series suggests individualized homeopathy can help to treat BPH, when the prescription is based on the laws and principles of homeopathy.

Keywords: Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH), lower urinary tract symptoms, Homeopathy.

Introduction

Prostate gland is an exocrine gland that functions as an accessory organ of the male reproductive system.¹ Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) is a benign enlargement of the prostate gland, commonly observed in men over 50 years of age, with peak incidence typically occurring between 60 and 70 years.² Studies highlight that nearly 50% of Indian men in this age group are affected by BPH. This condition is more frequently observed in urban populations, influenced by factors such as lifestyle changes, sedentary habits, and dietary patterns.³ A family history of BPH may increase the risk of developing the condition. Additionally, factors such as obesity and diabetes are linked to a higher risk of both BPH and associated lower urinary tract symptoms (LUTS). Maintaining regular physical activity has been shown to reduce the chances of developing BPH.⁴

The prostate gland has three lobes: one median and two lateral. BPH primarily affects the median lobe, with cellular proliferation occurring in the transitional zone, targeting glandular and stromal components. This growth compresses surrounding tissues, forming a pseudo-capsule or "surgical capsule." Hormonal factors, especially the conversion of testosterone to dihydrotestosterone (DHT) by 5 α -reductase play a key role, as DHT stimulates prostate tissue growth via androgen receptors.⁵

The primary symptoms of BPH may be voiding issues such as hesitancy, weak urinary flow, and a feeling of incomplete bladder emptying, frequent urination, urgency and urge incontinence. Acute urinary retention, characterized by painful bladder distension and inability to urinate may occur suddenly, often triggered by factors like excessive alcohol consumption, constipation, or prostatic infection.⁶ Sexual symptoms like

bilateral renal calculi and hemorrhoids. His brother had died due to myocardial infarction, and his sister suffers from cardiac issues and hypertension. Patient is fastidious and prefers company. He has a strong desire for fish, an aversion to milk, increased thirst, difficult to pass stool and is thermally hot. Based on repertorization (Figure 6) and corroboration with the Materia Medica, Lycopodium 200 was prescribed in a single dose.

Figure 6: Repertorization chart (case 2)

Follow up:

Date	Symptoms	Prescription
14-07-2023	Increased tendency to urinate at night accompanied by incontinence, difficult to pass stool Ultra sound: grade I prostatomegaly, bilateral renal calculus, Grade III fatty liver	Lycopodium 200 /4Doses (1-0-0) 1 dose per week. BT(1-1-1) for 1month
21-08-2023	Increased tendency to urinate at night accompanied by incontinence, constipation reduced, Generals were good	Lycopodium 200 /4Doses (1-0-0) 1 dose per week. BT(1-1-1) for 1month
25-09-2023	Increased tendency to urinate at night, incontinence slightly better, Generals were good	Lycopodium 200 /4Doses (1-0-0) 1 dose per week. BT(1-1-1) for 1month
27-12-2023	Increased tendency to urinate at night, incontinence reduced, Generals were good	Lycopodium 200 /4Doses (1-0-0) 1 dose per week. BT(1-1-1) for 1month
30-01-2024	Increased tendency to urinate at night, Generals were good, Ultra sound :grade I prostatomegaly, bilateral renal calculus, Grade I fatty liver	Lycopodium 200 /4Doses (1-0-0) 1 dose per week. BT(1-1-1) for 1month
27-03-2024	Increased tendency to urinate at night better, slight loin pain, Generals were good	Lycopodium 200 /4Doses (1-0-0) 1 dose per week. BT(1-1-1) for 1month
24-06-2024	Increased tendency to urinate at night reduced, loin pain reduced, Generals were good	Lycopodium 200 /4Doses (1-0-0) 1 dose per week. BT(1-1-1) for 1month
13-08-2024	Increased tendency to urinate at night reduced, generals are good, Ultra sound :normal prostate, left renal calculus, mild infiltration of liver	Lycopodium 200 /4Doses (1-0-0) 1 dose per week. BT(1-1-1) for 1month

Figure 7: Ultrasound image at the time of visit

Figure 8: Ultrasound image in the middle of treatment

Figure 9: Ultrasound image in the final report

CASE 3

A 47-year-old male patient presented with increased frequency of urination at night, along with a need to wait before urinating, followed by dribbling. He also reported experiencing vertigo with headache and pain in both heels, < early morning upon

waking. His past medical history included a hepatitis A infection 25 years ago, treated with conventional medicine, and he is currently under treatment for hypothyroidism. Family history revealed that his father had benign prostatic hyperplasia, while his mother has hypertension and diabetes mellitus. Mentally, the patient is mild-natured and loquacious. He has a strong desire for meat and is thermally hot. After Repertorization (Figure 10) and comparison with the Materia Medica, Sulphur 200 was prescribed in a single dose.

Figure 10: Repertorization chart (case 3)

Follow up:

Date	Symptoms	Prescription
23-07-2022	Increased frequency of urination at night, need to wait along before urinating, followed by dribbling, vertigo with headache, pain in both heels, Ultra sound :biliary sludge in GB, Mildly enlarged prostate with prostatic cyst, generals are good	Sulphur 200 /4 Doses (1-0-0) 1 dose per week BT(1-1-1) for 1month
26-10-2022	Increased frequency of urination at night, need to wait along before urinating, followed by dribbling, vertigo with headache reduced, pain in both heels better, generals were good	Sulphur 200 /4 Doses (1-0-0) 1 dose per week BT(1-1-1) for 1month
23-01-2023	Increased frequency of urination at night, need to wait along before urinating better, followed by dribbling, vertigo with headache Nil, pain in both heels reduced, generals were good	Sulphur 200 /8 Doses (1-0-0) 2 dose per week BT(1-1-1) for 1month
15-05-2023	Increased frequency of urination at night, need to wait along before urinating better, followed by dribbling, generals are good, Ultra sound :Mild Prostatomegaly with significant PVR	Sulphur 200 /8 Doses (1-0-0) 2 dose per week BT(1-1-1) for 1month
19-07-2023	Increased frequency of urination at night, need to wait along before urinating better, dribbling of urine reduced, generals were good	Sulphur 200 /8 Doses (1-0-0) 2 dose per week BT(1-1-1) for 1month
16-08-2023	Increased frequency of urination at night reduced, need to wait along before urinating better than before, dribbling of urine reduced, generals were good	Sulphur 200 /8 Doses (1-0-0) 2 dose per week BT(1-1-1) for 1month
18-10-2023	Increased frequency of urination at night reduced, other complaints are reduced, generals were good	Sulphur 200 /8 Doses (1-0-0) 2 dose per week BT(1-1-1) for 1month
12-12-2023	Increased frequency of urination at night -nil, generals were good, Ultra sound :normal study	Sac Lac /8 Doses (1-0-0) 2 dose per week BT(1-1-1) for 1 month

Figure 11: Ultrasound image at the time of visit

Figure 12: Ultrasound image in the middle of treatment

Figure 13: Ultrasound image in the final report

Result

Out of the three cases of BPH included in this case series, one case was grade 2 prostatomegaly and other two cases were grade 1 prostatomegaly. All cases presented with typical symptoms of BPH, including increased urinary frequency, weak or intermittent urine flow, and incomplete bladder emptying. Individualised homeopathic remedies were administered to each patient, with follow-ups conducted approximately every 30 days. Pre-treatment and post-treatment USG investigations revealed significant improvements in all three cases. The prostate gland returned to a normal size in two cases, while grade 2 was reduced to grade 1 in one case. This case series highlights the effectiveness of the constitutional approach in managing cases of BPH. Apart from prostatomegaly, one patient had a prostatic cyst and biliary sludge in the gallbladder, both of which completely resolved after treatment. Another patient had small bilateral renal calculi and mild fatty infiltration, along with prostatomegaly. His right renal calculus resolved, and the prostate returned to normal size after treatment. The indicated remedies in this case series was *Lycopodium clavatum* in two cases and *Sulphur* in one case. The above 3 cases are till now under our treatment for the same and other complaints also on & off.

Discussion

This case series demonstrates the effectiveness of homeopathic medicines in reducing prostate gland size in patients with BPH. Numerous published case reports, case series, and studies in homeopathy further support its potential as a treatment option for managing BPH.

A CCRH study on 231 BPH patients found significant symptom relief and reduction in prostate volume using remedies like Thuja, Sulphur, Pulsatilla, and Lycopodium over one year.¹¹ A clinical study conducted by Gupta et al. demonstrated the effectiveness of homeopathic remedies, including Lycopodium, Pulsatilla, Sulphur, and Calcarea carbonica, in the management of BPH.¹² Similarly, Lycopodium and Sulphur were identified as effective remedies in the context of this case study, demonstrating their potential utility in managing symptoms of BPH. A case series by Paital et al. provided ultrasonographic evidence demonstrating the effectiveness of a combined approach to homeopathic prescribing in managing BPH cases.¹³ A study by Bindu et al. found that homeopathic treatment significantly improved lower urinary tract symptoms in men with BPH compared to placebo. The most commonly used medicines included Lycopodium, Pulsatilla and Sulphur.¹⁴ The study by Dole et al. employed a prospective clinical design to evaluate the outcomes of homeopathic treatment in BPH and lower urinary tract symptom patients. Sabal serrulata was the most frequently prescribed medicine in the study.¹⁵ Hati et al. demonstrated that combined homeopathic treatment, integrating constitutional and organopathic approaches, was more effective in improving symptoms of BPH compared to either approach alone. Significant reductions in prostate volume and symptom scores were observed. Lycopodium and Sabal Serrulata were commonly used remedies in the trial.¹⁶ A study by Weinstein examined the use of homeopathic treatment for BPH, based on individual

symptoms, and remedies like Sabal Serrulata, Lycopodium, and Thuja helped improve urinary symptoms and overall health.¹⁷

Conclusion

Homeopathy emphasizes treating the patient holistically rather than focusing solely on the disease. The discussed case series demonstrate that homeopathic remedies chosen through the method of individualization, have the potential to alleviate symptoms of BPH and to reduce the size of prostate gland.

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